

1 **Supplementary Information** for “*Vacuum-gap electrostatic multilayer actuators*
2 *for space robotics*”

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16 1. Actuation dependency on environment pressure

17 Gas pressure is perhaps the most critical parameter for applications that use high voltages in a
18 vacuum. The goal of this experiment is to provide an estimation of the pressure threshold for the
19 safe operation of our actuators. The test consists in integrating a single-unit optimized V-EBM in
20 the vacuum test bench, loading it with a force of 1 N via a soft spring, and applying a 6 kV
21 switching signal with 5 Hz actuation frequency for a duration of 330 s. The experiment was
22 initiated at a pressure as low as $2.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mbar, that was increased up to 0.1 mbar throughout the
23 experiment duration.

24 The relevant actuation parameters are plotted in Supplementary Fig. 1. The device exhibited a
25 constant stroke of just under 1 mm up to the pressure of $\sim 10^{-2}$ mbar, above which it stopped
26 actuating due to electrical discharges in the residual gas in the vacuum chamber. This caused
27 current saturation in our amplifiers, preventing further operation. Short-term exposure (~ 20 s)
28 did not inflict any evident critical damage to the device, as it continued operating normally once
29 the pressure was reduced.

30 2. Discussion regarding materials compatibility with space environment

31 Exposure to extreme conditions in space will undoubtedly lead to degradation of materials, loss of
32 performance, and failure in time (*I*). Therefore, it is critical that suitable materials are chosen to
33 ensure adequate performance throughout the duration of the mission and degradation or failure
34 only after its completion. Consequently, materials must meet strict requirements in terms of
35 thermal stability, have low outgassing, be resistant to ultraviolet (UV) radiation and ionizing
36 radiation, and sustain prolonged exposure to atomic oxygen, the latter being particularly relevant
37 in low Earth orbit (*I*, *2*).

38 However, most applications do not require all these criteria to be met simultaneously (*3*), the
39 selection of materials being tailored to application-specific considerations. For example, a
40 spacecraft thermal blanket that is continuously exposed to the environment must fit to a large
41 degree all these criteria, whereas an actuation system that operates an optical instrument would
42 have strict limitations in terms of the release of volatile substances that can deposit on sensitive
43 optical surfaces but may be protected against extreme temperatures or non-penetrating radiation.
44 Over the past six decades these critical challenges have been extensively studied and documented
45 in exhaustive works, that include books (*4–6*), technical reports (*2*, *7*), and reviews (*3*, *8–10*).

46 In this context, a variety of polymeric materials have been emphasized, such as polyimides (PI),
47 fluoropolymers like fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE),
48 polyesters like biaxially-oriented polyethylene terephthalate (BOPET), polyamides, e.g. nylon,
49 polyether ether ketone (PEEK), silicone elastomers, epoxy resins, and many others.

50 **Dielectric.** The dielectric chosen for the V-EBM is PI, which is perhaps one of the most common
51 polymers in space applications. PI is generally characterized by excellent thermal stability, it
52 withstands both very high and very low temperatures (typically from below -200 to over 300 °C),
53 it has good resistance to radiation and good dielectric properties (*I*), the latter being also a critical
54 factor for the electrostatic working principle of the V-EBM. PI films have been extensively

55 employed in space applications. One of the most recent and notable applications is the sunshield
56 of the James Webb Space Telescope, which has a surface roughly the size of a tennis court and
57 uses five layers of thin PI films (Kapton by DuPont) with thicknesses of 25 and 50 μm (11).
58 Therefore, the range of dielectric materials for V-EBM can include other PI brands as well, such
59 as the Kapton films by DuPont, with space-proven abilities and electrical and mechanical
60 properties similar to those we currently employ.

61 **Dielectric strength of the PI films at high temperature.** We performed a dielectric strength
62 measurement of our PI film in relation to temperature. For this, a single 25.4 μm thick PI film was
63 placed between two electrodes: a brass mass with geometry suggested in the standards IEC 60243
64 1 and ASTM D149 for dielectric strength of thin films and laminates, that serves as the high voltage
65 electrode, and a large, polished aluminum surface as the ground electrode. Breakdown tests were
66 conducted by applying a voltage ramp of 500 V/s in an oven at 26 (ambient temperature), 60, 100
67 and 145°C. Five repetitions were performed for each temperature. Besides relying on the oven
68 integrated temperature sensor, the temperature was confirmed on the mass with a thermal camera.

69 The results are displayed in Supplementary Fig. 2A. We found that the dielectric strength does not
70 decrease with increasing temperature up to 100 °C, staying well-above the minimum of 236 V/ μm
71 indicated in the material datasheet. The median dielectric strength measured at 26, 60 and 100°C
72 is roughly 273, 327 and 308 V/ μm respectively, and, if normalized to the dielectric thickness of
73 the V-EBM, these correspond to roughly 230, 280 and 260% of the maximum voltage of 6 kV
74 employed for the characterization of the actuator. However, at 145 °C, we noticed a tangible
75 decrease in the dielectric strength. The median dielectric strength value at this temperature stands
76 at about 236 V/ μm , which still corresponds to 200% of the maximum field applied during V-EBM
77 actuation. The median values at all temperatures show a dielectric strength at least twice the
78 maximum electric field strength we employed during actuation.

79 **Dielectric strength of gamma irradiated films.** We exposed four small samples of our PI
80 dielectric to gamma radiation. Each sample was irradiated with a dose of 117, 474, 1025, or 1475
81 kGy. These are large doses, considering that the average radiation dose absorbed in Si due to
82 charged particles on the Moon is $10.2 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{Gy}/\text{hour}$ (12).

83 The samples did not suffer any visual changes, and no macroscopic mechanical alterations of these
84 films were noticed. In addition, we tested the dielectric strength of the irradiated films. For this,
85 each sample was covered on both sides with overlapping circular electrodes (Nisshin high-
86 conductivity carbon double-sided tape) with a diameter of 1 cm, to which a unipolar voltage ramp
87 of 500 V/s was applied. The dielectric strength testing was repeated on four non-irradiated control
88 samples. The measured dielectric strength is plotted in Supplementary Fig. 2B. The preliminary
89 data indicate that gamma irradiation up to 1475 kGy does not adversely affect the dielectric
90 strength of our material. Both the irradiated and control samples have significantly higher
91 dielectric strength than the minimum indicated by the manufacturer, which is 6 kV/mil or about
92 236 V/ μm .

93 The irradiation was performed at Calliope Gamma Radiation Facility at ENEA - Casaccia
94 Research Center in Rome (13), one of Italy's foremost national laboratories for energy and

95 advanced technology research. The facility is equipped with a pool-type gamma irradiation plant
96 with a Cobalt-60 radio-isotropic source array, of an average energy of 1.25 MeV, a dosimetry
97 laboratory, and a laboratory for the characterization and treatment of samples before and after
98 irradiation. More information and images about the irradiation plant can be found in (13).

99 The samples were irradiated in air, at room temperature. The irradiation campaign lasted a total of
100 602 hours. At the end of the gamma ray exposure test, the specimens were brought to the
101 characterization laboratory of the Calliope facility. The calculation of the absorbed dose
102 considered the natural decay of the Cobalt-60 source. For determining the dose rates and the
103 absorbed dose of the irradiated samples, the ESR-alanine dosimetric system was used in
104 accordance with ISO/ASTM 51607:2013. The doses and the irradiation times are given in
105 Supplementary Table 2 for each sample. The irradiation was performed and the results provided
106 by the facility personnel.

107 **Frames.** The frames and the interfacial elements were made of pure glass-reinforced PI resin (85N,
108 Arlon), a high glass transition temperature material that is often used in high-performance
109 electronics applications. The Arlon 85N material was tested according to ASTM E595-93 and has
110 a 0.78 % total mass loss (TML), 0.01 % collected volatile condensable materials (CVCM) and
111 0.27 % water vapor recovery (WVR) (data from application notes sent to us by the manufacturer).
112 This material was implemented in space missions, for example, in printed wiring boards (PWBs)
113 for the Near-Infrared Spectrometer and Photometer of ESA's Euclid mission (14).

114 **Adhesive.** The adhesive (Pyrалux LF0100 Sheet Adhesive, DuPont), has TML 0.94 %, CVCM
115 0.06 % and WVR 0.42 % (from Nasa Outgassing Database, reference GSC17366) and complies
116 with the criteria of maximum 1.0 % TML and 0.10 % CVCM of NASA specification SP-R-0022.
117 Pyralux is a range of adhesives developed by DuPont, typically used in high-performance PWBs
118 and flexible circuits. Pyralux LF and AP adhesives have been employed in space missions such as
119 Mars Pathfinder, Hubble Space Telescope, Cassini, Mars Exploration Rover, Mars Phoenix
120 Lander, and Mars Space Laboratory (from application notes sent to us by the vendor).

121 **Coating.** Parylene C is common in space missions and is often used as a coating for the protection
122 of electronic circuits, sensors, optical instruments, and other spacecraft components. Previously,
123 Parylene C was employed in the Juno space probe that orbits Jupiter as a protective coating for the
124 electronics of its JunoCam visible light onboard camera. As of 2025, NASA's Outgassing
125 Database for Spacecraft Materials includes several Parylene C variants classified as low-
126 outgassing materials.

127 **Gripper.** The body of the compliant gripper was made of PTFE, a material characterized by
128 superior outgassing properties, a very high melting temperature (more than 300 °C), a low friction
129 coefficient and good dielectric properties. Historically, it has been used in space applications such
130 as cable insulations, thermal blankets, seals, bearings, etc. However, its low resistance to radiation
131 and atomic oxygen corrosion, which can increase its hardness or make it brittle, can be a limiting
132 factor. Depending on the specific implementation, these effects must be considered and, if
133 necessary, protective measures or alternative solutions must be investigated, especially where
134 polymer flexibility is essential, such as in a compliant mechanism.

135 We chose PTFE because of its low outgassing, which is important for achieving low pressures in
136 our vacuum system in a timely manner. However, in structural applications where long exposure
137 to radiation is imminent, other polymers, such as PI, can be explored instead of PTFE.

138 **3. Actuators fabrication**

139 The generalized fabrication process is depicted in Supplementary Fig. 3. The thin PI films, the
140 adhesives, and PDMS masks for electrode deposition were cut into the required circular shapes
141 with a laser cutter, whereas the frames were cut with a desktop CNC machine (Supplementary Fig.
142 3A). The fabrication of the electrodes consisted of the application of 100 μm thick PDMS masks
143 (Wacker ELASTOSIL® 2030 on its primer) and the subsequent sputtering of Cu on one side of
144 the PI films (Supplementary Fig. 3B). The electrodes have an annular shape and thin rectangular
145 appendages (dimensions presented in Supplementary Table 1) for electrical connections with
146 power cables or other units. These small appendages protrude between the frames and the dielectric
147 away from the electroactive area. The assembly of each unit of the preliminary V-EBM stack
148 follows a straightforward procedure of overlaying and joining all materials with double-sided
149 adhesives (Supplementary Fig. 3C). Stacking is achieved by mechanically interconnecting the
150 units through the central VHB adhesive (Supplementary Fig. 3D). The outer units of the stack are
151 attached to two interfacial elements designed to embed the actuator in the testing setup. In practical
152 applications, these elements could be avoided by integrating the actuators directly into the driven
153 mechanisms through their central adhesives. The interfacial elements are 3D printed in the case of
154 the preliminary V-EBM (Grey Pro resin, Formlabs 2) due to simplicity and short process duration
155 or made of a PI-fiberglass and Pyralux adhesive laminate for the optimized V-EBM. Furthermore,
156 these elements were not included in the final device mass or volume considerations and power
157 density calculations because they do not influence the actuation performance, and their design can
158 vary between applications, up to the possibility of being fully omitted.

159 The assembly of the optimized V-EBM unit was done under high-pressure and high-temperature
160 conditions. For this, all the components, i.e., the two PI films, the adhesives, the frames, and the
161 PI interfacial elements, were pressed together in a rigid parallel plate Al clamp and placed in an
162 oven at 190 ° C for two hours (Supplementary Fig. 3E). Electrical wires are attached to the
163 electrode appendages prior to Parylene-C deposition.

164 The actuators were equipped with small vent holes, each consisting of a $\text{Ø}1$ mm coaxial hole in
165 the bottom interfacial element, aligned with a hole in the corresponding PI film with a diameter of
166 ≈ 0.6 mm. The hole in the interfacial elements was produced during the materials cutting phase
167 (Supplementary Fig. 3A), whereas the hole in the PI film was created by piercing with a $\text{Ø}0.6$ mm
168 needle after the assembly, but prior to the Parylene-C coating. This configuration allows air to
169 escape from the internal volume of the actuator, ensuring pressure equilibrium with the external
170 vacuum environment. In stacked configurations, the venting holes of individual units are
171 interconnected. Before coating with Parylene C (Supplementary Fig. 3F), a porous tissue was
172 inserted into the vent hole; this allows the Parylene to occlude the tissue without penetrating inside
173 the device. During the initial stages of the deposition process, the tissue permits venting, and it
174 was subsequently removed after deposition. The thickness of 7 μm was chosen because it is a good
175 compromise between deposition time and device stiffness, while still providing protection against
176 electrical arcs.

177 4. Actuators dimensions and mass

178 In the case of three-unit preliminary V-EBM, the total thickness of the device is $L = 3.15$ mm,
179 whereas for the optimized single unit, $L = 1.20$ mm. L does not include the thickness of the
180 interfacial elements, which can be tailored to application specific requirements. The exact
181 dimension of each constitutive element is indicated in Supplementary Table 1.

182 The mass of the three-unit V-EBM is 5.3 g. The mass of the optimized V-EBM is only 0.7 g. Its
183 volume in free state, given by the cylindrical envelope of its frames, is about 1.09 cm³. This value
184 can be useful for payload volume calculations and was used in the power-to-volume estimation.
185 The real volume, bounded by the external surfaces of the parylene coating, in the contracted state
186 is 0.53 cm³, and at the maximum device elongation of 2 mm (Supplementary Fig. 11) – 1.32 cm³.

187 5. Actuators scaling

188 Scaling rules for EBM devices have been discussed and validated in our previous work on liquid-
189 based EBMs (15), and they rely on the assumption that the electrostatic force output is proportional
190 to the applied voltage squared and the derivative of the capacitance with respect to the stroke:

$$191 \quad F \propto V^2 \frac{dC}{dx} \propto \frac{V^2}{t} \frac{dA(x)}{dx} \propto E^2 t \frac{dA(x)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

192 where F is the force output, V is the applied voltage, C is the capacitance of the zipped portion (in
193 a given actuator configuration), x is the stroke, t is the total dielectric thickness in the zipped region
194 (which can be assumed constant with respect to x), $E = V/t$ is the applied electric field, $A(x)$ is the
195 area of the zipped region (proportional to the squared diameter of the actuator and variable with
196 x).

197 Assuming that the radial dimensions scale by a factor s_r with respect to a base case scenario (i.e.,
198 A scales with s_r^2) while the dielectric film thickness t and applied electric field stay unchanged,
199 then the stroke scales by a factor s_r (same as the radial dimensions, leaving the strains unchanged)
200 in the presence of a force that is s_r times larger than that of the base case scenario. The resulting
201 mechanical work performed in a cycle thus scales with s_r^2 .

202 A major difference with respect to the liquid-based implementation concerns the scaling of the
203 energy density (i.e., the cyclic mechanical work per unit device mass). The mass of a liquid-based
204 EBM is dominated by the liquid mass, which scales with the cube of the radial scale factor, s_r^3 .
205 Therefore, the energy density of a fluid-based EBM approximately scales with s_r^{-1} : small-scale
206 actuators feature a higher energy density, because of the lower fluid volume. In vacuum-based
207 devices, the mass is expected to scale with the surface area of the actuator in a broad range of
208 dimensions, making the energy density constant throughout the different scales. This trend would
209 be broken at large scales, where larger structural masses might be required to prevent device
210 buckling and bending.

211 In general, removing the liquid dielectric gap thus leads to higher energy densities (because of
212 lower masses) over a broader range of radial dimensions.

213 It is worth noticing that, under the assumption that the dielectric film thickness stays constant upon
214 scaling, the voltage requested to achieve a target electric field stays unchanged. Scaling the
215 thickness by a factor s_t and leaving the voltage unchanged leads to a reduction of a factor s_t in the
216 force output. Increasing both the dielectric thickness and the voltage of a factor s_t (hence leaving
217 the electric field unchanged) leads to an increase in force by a factor s_t , as shown by the equation
218 above.

219 6. Experimental setup

220 **Actuator characterization.** The layout of the main experimental setup is indicated in
221 Supplementary Fig. 4A. The glass dome in which the actuators are tested has a cylindrical internal
222 volume with a diameter of 60 mm and height of 100 mm.

223 The tested actuator is mounted in the setup by fixing one of its interfacial elements to a rigid
224 supporting structure and attaching the other to the preloading spring, so that the V-EBM extension
225 is unidirectional (Supplementary Fig. 4B). The spring, and hence the actuator, is extended by the
226 motorized linear feedthrough equipped with position feedback. The soft spring has coefficient
227 $k=0.032$ N/mm and an initial force $F_0 \approx 0.75$ N which were measured with an accurate laser meter
228 (Keyence LK-G-152) and a force sensor (Rb-Phi-118). The force acting on the device was
229 estimated as

$$230 \quad F = k * \Delta s + F_0, \quad (2)$$

231 where $\Delta s = s - s_0$ is the stroke of the motor from the position in which the spring elongation
232 begins, s_0 , to the motor position at any given moment in time, s . The maximum elastic elongation
233 of the spring is 114 mm. The start of the spring elongation was detected with the high-fps camera,
234 and its corresponding motor position value was registered for each device prior to each set of
235 experiments.

236 The advantages of employing a soft spring are multiple. Firstly, it offers the possibility of applying
237 a wide force range without the need to open the vacuum system every time the applied force must
238 be changed. Secondly, the soft spring avoids the inertial effects attributed to large hanging masses
239 and makes it possible to apply a quasi-constant force even when the device is dynamically
240 operated. Crucially, it also avoids the risk of damaging the glass chamber by wobbling heavy
241 hanging masses. Furthermore, the very long soft spring compensates for any small misalignment
242 in the system and for the stroke of the V-EBMs. The stroke introduces trivial real-time force
243 variations, and as described in the Methods section of the main manuscript, a V-EBM unit stroke
244 of 1 mm produces a force variation of just 0.032 N, which in the applied force range of 1 - 4.25 N
245 corresponds to a force error of 0.75 to 3.2%.

246 **EBM temperature response.** The layout of the experimental setup employed for temperature
247 measurement is indicated in Supplementary Fig. 5A. An optimized single-unit V-EBM
248 (Supplementary Fig. 5B) is mounted in a horizontal orientation in a vacuum chamber without
249 direct contact with the chamber walls. The actuator is constrained on its top side via a rigid
250 structure made of two 0.5 mm thick PI-fiberglass laminate (Arlon 85N) beams oriented in a cross
251 shape, both fixed on the chamber walls (Supplementary Fig. 5C). Above this structure, the
252 chamber is closed with an IR-transparent viewport (BVPZ64ZNSE, Torr Scientific). An IR camera
253 (FLIR A70 with 51° FOV lens) is placed atop the viewport, slightly angled w.r.t. to the flat
254 horizontal surface of the V-EBM, such as to have a good view on the actuator without producing
255 self-reflection. The thin beams of the support structure ensure a minimal obstruction of the camera
256 view. Also, from the top and pointing towards the frame of the device is a laser meter (Keyence
257 LK-G152), intended to confirm actuation and estimate the stroke at low actuation frequency. The
258 V-EBM is mechanically loaded from the bottom side through the steel spring, connected in series
259 to a vacuum-compatible load cell and to the linear vacuum feedthrough. In a similar fashion to the
260 main characterization procedure depicted in Supplementary Fig. 4, the movement of the linear
261 feedthrough adjusts the length of the spring and thus dictates the preload. However, here a visual
262 estimation of the spring position/elongation was not possible due to the opacity of the chamber,
263 hence a vacuum-compatible load cell (KD24S 20N, ME-Meßsysteme) was connected in series to
264 the spring to accurately monitor the applied force.

265 A total of 10 temperature markers were attached to the upper surface of the V-EBM actuator: 8
266 arranged at regular angular intervals on the top electrode, and 2 attached to the connection of the
267 electrode to the wires (Supplementary Fig. 5B). All markers have a circular shape ($\varnothing_{\text{marker}} = 4 \text{ mm}$)
268 and are made of 3 layers of PI-silicone adhesive tape each (Caplinq PIT0.5S). The motivation
269 behind employing such markers is that accurate temperature readings cannot be taken directly from
270 the surface of the actuator because of the high reflectivity of the copper electrodes, which coupled
271 with the high IR transmissivity of the very thin Parylene-C coating, lead to reflecting the IR
272 emission of the environment. We estimated an emissivity value as high as 0.96 for the marker
273 material, thus making IR-based temperature measurement viable. The emissivity was estimated by
274 measuring with the camera the incident power while observing a black body, a grey body (our
275 marker PI material) and a white body in the same conditions and relying on the incident power
276 formulations provided by the camera manufacturer.

277 We estimated the IR transmittance of the viewport by establishing a linear fitting between values
278 of incident power measured with and without the viewport on the same object at several
279 temperatures. We obtained a viewport transmittance of 0.71, which is the same as indicated by the
280 viewport manufacturer. The results provided in this work account for the transmittance of the
281 viewport.

282 **Gripper.** For the gripper experiments, the glass dome, the linear feedthrough and the motor are
283 inverted, so that these components are upside down w.r.t. Supplementary Fig. 4, as can be seen in
284 Fig. 5B, Supplementary Fig. 6 and Supplementary Movies 2 and 3. The elastic connection used in
285 the main characterization of the actuator was substituted here with a rigid interface between the
286 gripper and the feedthrough. As a result, the motor moves the gripper mechanism directly on a
287 vertical axis.

288 7. Data acquisition and processing

289 We designed and implemented custom algorithms for signal generation and data acquisition in
290 Matlab Simulink Real-Time, which were executed on a Speedgoat target computer. Of particular
291 note here is that this computer triggered each camera frame, hence synchronizing the actuator
292 stroke measurements with data acquired from other sensors, such as the motor position and,
293 subsequently, force. The acquired video was processed post-experimentally using edge detection
294 techniques from the MATLAB Image Processing Toolbox (Supplementary Fig. 7). The conversion
295 coefficient from pixels to millimeters was determined by filming an object with clear edges and
296 known dimensions. The conversion was performed during post-processing.

297 Video frames were acquired at 250 fps for force-stroke characterization and at 500 fps for
298 frequency characterization. In addition to the high-fps camera, we employed a secondary camera
299 for high-resolution media data (Canon EOS 80D with Canon EF 50 mm lens).

300 8. Actuators characterization process

301 We define elongation (or instantaneous elongation) - in millimeters, as the mechanical elongation
302 or stretch of the actuators at any moment (applied voltage $U \geq 0$). The elongation is zero under
303 the baseline condition of maximum possible contraction without external load.

304 We define stroke as the difference between the maximum and minimum elongation in each cycle.

305 **Driving voltage.** Typical driving strategies of a liquid-based EMSs consist in applying switching
306 high voltage signals, often square or sine waves (15–19). These waveforms periodically invert the
307 polarity across the electrodes. This is typically achieved either using four-quadrant high-voltage
308 amplifiers capable of sourcing both positive and negative voltages relative to a common ground,
309 or by employing high-voltage switching circuits and/or multichannel unipolar voltage supplies that
310 electrically 'swap' the electrode connections to reverse polarity.

311 We adopted the latter driving strategy by alternately applying a positive voltage to one electrode
312 and simultaneously grounding the other. Positive voltage and grounding were applied on opposite
313 electrodes in an alternating manner, so that at any moment only one electrode is energized, and the
314 other is grounded in any actuation unit (Supplementary Fig. 8). This results, in essence, in
315 switching voltage and current direction across the load (our actuators).

316 Furthermore, in the case of our transducers, force variation under DC conditions occurs slowly
317 (with time constants significantly exceeding several minutes). Therefore, charge accumulation is
318 not expected to influence dynamic actuation involving switching voltage polarity.

319 We applied voltage to each electrode (or group of interconnected electrodes in a stack) from two
320 separate sources, although the same driving strategy can be alternatively achieved with H-bridges
321 or other methods (19, 20). The tested voltage amplitudes were 4, 5, and 6 kV.

322 The voltage was delivered to the electrodes from outside the vacuum system through an electrical
323 feedthrough (Pfeiffer), which is a two-pole electrical interface made of ceramically insulated Ni

324 conductors and integrated into a CF63 flange, designed to provide a pathway for the signal into
325 the chamber without compromising the vacuum environment.

326 **Force-stroke characterization.** The force-stroke behavior of both actuators was determined under
327 identical conditions in terms of the applied high voltage signal and force. The characterization was
328 performed at pressures below $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mbar. The loading was performed only axially, otherwise
329 operation is compromised, the displacements of the actuator kinematically resembling the linear
330 motion of piston.

331 We applied voltages with amplitude of 4, 5, and 6 kV, with a signal frequency of 2.5 Hz,
332 corresponding to an actuation frequency of 5 Hz. The voltage signal was applied for the entire
333 duration of slowly loading the actuators with a force ramp from 1 to 4.25 N at a rate of 0.0583 N/s.
334 The force rate is deliberately slow compared to the actuation dynamics, to ensure that at an
335 actuation frequency of 5 Hz, the discretized force can be considered constant on each actuation
336 cycle.

337 The maximum applied force of 4.25 N represents the upper force boundary of our setup. Although
338 the blocked force of the V-EBM slightly surpasses it when the actuator is under the maximum
339 applied voltage of 6 kV, it can be considered a conservative blocked force of the device as it does
340 not misrepresent the force-stroke characteristic in any significant manner.

341 The videoframe acquisition frequency of 250 fps allowed a resolution of 50 data points per
342 actuation cycle.

343 Supplementary Fig. 10 and Supplementary Fig. 11 illustrate the instantaneous elongation of the
344 actuators. The lower blocked force of the three-unit actuator is attributed to a different
345 manufacturing procedure and errors introduced during manual assembly.

346 The optimized V-EBM provided a force output surpassing the threshold of 4.25 N. Its low mass
347 of just 0.7 g leads to force-to-mass ratio of over 6000 N/kg.

348 **Frequency response.** Two frequency tests were performed on the optimized V-EBM to determine
349 its dynamic and quasi-static behaviors.

350 The dynamic behavior was evaluated with a linear up-chirp from 1 to 100 Hz (actuation frequency)
351 in 60 s, while the voltage amplitude and the preload were kept constant. The applied voltage
352 amplitude was either 4, 5 or 6 kV, while the preload was set to 1.5 N. The dynamic response can
353 be seen in Supplementary Fig. 12.

354 Resonance. The stroke frequency response of the V-EBM prototype shown in Fig. 3F in the main
355 paper shows a resonant behavior in the range 60-80 Hz. This is not due to the actuator's own
356 dynamics, but rather to the structural dynamics of the spring used to preload the V-EBM, which
357 holds distributed stiffness and mass that lead to longitudinal waves propagation.

358 Because the V-EBM elastic stiffness (estimated from its force-displacement measured response at
359 no voltage) is several orders of magnitude larger than that of the spring ($\sim 10^3$ N/m vs. $\sim 10^1$ N/m),

360 the natural frequencies of the waves travelling along the spring can be calculated assuming that
361 the latter has fixed ends. Noting that the spring mass m is 1.53 g, and its stiffness k is 32 N/m, the
362 natural frequency of the first vibration mode is thus given by $f_1 = 0.5\sqrt{k/m} \approx 72$ Hz. Longitudinal
363 waves propagation in a range close to the first natural frequency cause significant deformations of
364 the spring, with a consequent perturbation in the V-EBM measured stroke.

365 The quasistatic behavior was investigated with an up-chirp from 0.1 to 1 Hz (actuation frequency)
366 in 60 s for the three voltage amplitudes and the 1.5 N preload. The quasistatic response is depicted
367 in Supplementary Fig. 13.

368 **Contraction, speed and power calculations.** The contraction was calculated as follows:

369
$$c(\%) = \frac{x_0 - x}{x_0 + L} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

370 where x_0 is the elongation under mechanical load when no voltage is applied and is provided by
371 the elastic response of the actuators, x is the instantaneous elongation of the actuator during
372 actuation, and L is the geometric length of the actuators, given by their constitutive elements:
373 frames, dielectric films, and adhesives. The total device thickness L is significantly influenced by
374 the thickness of the frames, each frame being ~ 0.5 mm (Supplementary Table 1). Thinner frames
375 would significantly increase the contraction value. Furthermore, in applications in which the
376 actuated structure fits within the inner perimeter of the frames, their thickness is trivial for
377 actuation performance. Therefore, if this thickness is not included in the calculation, the
378 contraction of the single unit reaches 68 % as opposed to ~ 40 %.

379 Fig. 3E shows the cyclical peak contraction obtained during the force ramp test (force-stroke
380 characterization), whereas Supplementary Fig. 14 shows the contraction value at 45 Hz from the
381 frequency sweep tests.

382 The contraction rate was expressed as the derivative of contraction w.r.t. time (i.e., the acquisition
383 period):

384
$$c_{rate} = \frac{dc}{dt}, \quad (4)$$

385 and surpassed 2500 % s⁻¹.

386 The instantaneous velocity was calculated as the derivative of elongation w.r.t. time:

387
$$v(x) = \frac{dx}{dt}, \quad (5)$$

388 and reaches 670 mm/s in the contraction direction at around 45 Hz (Fig. 3G and Supplementary
389 Fig. 14).

390 The average positive work and average power delivered during each cycle are shown in
 391 Supplementary Fig. 15, Supplementary Fig. 16 for both actuators. The average power was
 392 estimated from the work performed during half of the actuation period (positive work interval).
 393 The obtained value is conservative because the contraction typically happens significantly faster
 394 than half the period considered period due to the pull-in effect.

395 9. Heat dissipation considerations

396 Let us assume that V-EBM is holding a load in a fully zipped configuration, subject to a constant
 397 DC voltage. The dissipated power can be estimated as

$$398 \quad P_{loss,dc} = \frac{U_{dc}^2 \sigma_p A}{2t_p} \quad (6)$$

399 where σ_p is the dielectric polymer conductivity, A is the electrode area, t_p is the thickness of a
 400 single dielectric layer, and U_{dc} the applied DC voltage. The conductivity of the reference PI
 401 material, in the presence of an electric field, was previously measured to be $\sigma_p = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-15}$ S/m.
 402 Assuming a working voltage equal to the maximum voltage used in these tests ($U = 6$ kV) and
 403 knowing the geometry and mass ($m = 0.7$ g) of a single V-EBM unit leads to a dissipated power
 404 density $P_{loss,dc}/m \sim 1$ μ W/g.

405 In the case of high-frequency actuation with an AC driving voltage, a bottleneck in terms of heat
 406 dissipation comes from the compliant electrodes. By approximating the device as a series R-C
 407 branch (with the resistance R accounting for the electrode losses, and the capacitance C
 408 representing the V-EBM in a lumped manner), the dissipated power can be expressed as

$$409 \quad P_{loss,ac} = \frac{U_{ac}^2}{2} \frac{R}{R^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\omega C}\right)^2}, \quad (7)$$

410 assuming an AC driving signal with amplitude U_{ac} and angular frequency ω . We obtained an
 411 estimate for R by measuring the series resistance of a zipped V-EBM with an LCR meter, and the
 412 point-to-point resistance between two regions at opposite ends of a same electrode, consistently
 413 obtaining values on the order of tens of Ω . Assuming $U_{ac} = 6$ kV, $\omega = 2\pi \cdot 100$ Hz (i.e., at the
 414 upper bound of our tested frequency range), and C equal to the nominal zipped capacitance (which
 415 is a conservative assumption for the calculation) leads to a dissipated power density
 416 $P_{loss,ac}/m \sim 10^{-1}$ mW/g.

417 10. Gripper

418 The gripper is a compliant mechanism that leverages the bending of four thin cantilevers induced
 419 by the contraction of the V-EBM. During operation, the actuator is attached, on one side, to the
 420 fixed end of the gripper, and on the other, to a stiff, but movable short transversal beam (Fig. 5).

421 The V-EBM contraction reduces the distance between the two beams, thus bending the cantilevers
422 and closing the gripper. The elastic behavior of the gripper was investigated in atmosphere by
423 manually displacing the transversal beam and measuring its displacement (laser meter Keyence
424 LK G152) and the applied force respectively (load cell Me-Systeme KD24S). The loading curve,
425 which corresponds to the action of closing the gripper, was plotted in Supplementary Fig. 18
426 (yellow curve) and was associated with the force-elongation behavior of the preliminary V-EBM
427 (blue curve for the elastic response, orange curve for the actuator response with voltage applied).

428 The working point of the gripper-EBM set for the grasping test shown in Fig. 5B is indicated by
429 the purple marker in Supplementary Fig. 18. This has been estimated from the frames of the
430 measurement camera collected during the tests, which allowed measuring the vertical stroke Δx
431 of the V-EBM (i.e., elongation variation) from the initial configuration (voltage off) to the final
432 grasping configuration (voltage on). The normal (horizontal) grasping force on the rock sample
433 during the test can be estimated by comparing the force F_1 requested to bring the gripper to the
434 final target configuration (winning the gripper elasticity), and the force F_2 that the V-EBM can
435 apply in such a final configuration:

$$436 \quad F_g = (F_2 - F_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta y} \quad (8)$$

437 where $\Delta x = 1$ mm is the vertical stroke of the V-EBM, $\Delta y = 6.2$ mm is the variation of the
438 horizontal distance between the jaws of the gripper. The factor $\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta y}$ is a Jacobian factor that reports
439 the vertical component of the force that contributes to grasping ($F_2 - F_1 = 0.44$ N) to the horizontal
440 direction (i.e., the grasping direction), leading to $F_g \approx 70$ mN.

441 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES**

442

443 **Supplementary Fig. 1. Behavior of the optimized V-EBM under variable environment**
 444 **pressure.** Peak positive current (left Y axis) supplied by one of the amplifiers and actuator's stroke
 445 (right Y axis), as functions of environment pressure. The measurements were performed on a
 446 single-unit optimized V-EBM, actuating at 5 Hz under 6 kV and a preload of 1 N. The supplied
 447 current saturates at 100 μA (high voltage supply limit) indicating electrical discharges in the
 448 residual gas at pressures over 10^{-2} mbar, at which the actuation ceases.

449

450 **Supplementary Fig. 2. Dielectric characterization of the PI films.** Dielectric strength (left Y
 451 axes) and its extrapolation to voltage across the combined thickness of two PI films (right Y axes),
 452 as functions of: (A) temperature; (B) gamma irradiation.

453

454 **Supplementary Fig. 3. Fabrication steps of the two actuators.** (A) Shaping the components
 455 using laser cutting and CNC milling/cutting. (B) Deposition of Cu electrodes. (C) Assembly of the
 456 units of the preliminary V-EBM. (D) Stacking. (E) Assembly of the optimized V-EBM. (F)
 457 Parylene C coating.

458

459 **Supplementary Fig. 4. Experimental test bench.** (A) Photography of the experimental test bench
 460 with indication of its main components. (B) Schematic of the preloading mechanism.

461

462 **Supplementary Fig. 5. Setup for the IR-based temperature measurements.** (A) Schematic of
 463 the test bench. (B) Single-unit optimized V-EBM used in the measurement, with the IR-emissive
 464 PI markers visible on the thermally active surface of the device. (C) Photography of the EBM
 465 mounting in the vacuum chamber for the IR experiments. The EBM and its support - a thin
 466 structure made of PI-fiberglass laminate, are visible inside the chamber. The IR-transparent
 467 viewport has been removed for a clear view of the contents of the chamber.

468

469 **Supplementary Fig. 6. Schematic of the gripper test bench.**

470

471 **Supplementary Fig. 7. The video processing methodology.** *Left:* A video frame showing the
 472 lower tip of one of the V-EBMs. The black lines represent the detected edges, whereas the colored
 473 marker - the middle of the tip width. *Right:* The two plots indicate the vertical displacement of the
 474 tip within the frame.

475

476 **Supplementary Fig. 8. Applied high voltage signal.** The two sources apply the dashed signals
 477 and alternatively energize opposite electrodes, whereas the solid black line represents the
 478 equivalent applied voltage across the actuator.

479

480 **Supplementary Fig. 9. Three-unit preliminary V-EBM contraction as function of applied**
 481 **force**

482

483 **Supplementary Fig. 10. Response of the three-unit actuator to a force ramp from 1 to 4.25 N.**

484

485 **Supplementary Fig. 11. Response of the optimized V-EBM to a force ramp from 1 to 4.25 N.**

486

487 **Supplementary Fig. 12. Dynamic tests frequency response of the optimized V-EBM.** *Left:*
 488 Snippet of the frequency sweep test showing the instantaneous elongation of the single-unit
 489 actuator under an up-chirp high voltage signal at 4, 5, and 6 kV from 1 to 6.6 Hz. *Right:* Snippet
 490 of the instantaneous elongation at approximately 100 Hz.

491

492 **Supplementary Fig. 13. Quasistatic tests frequency response of the optimized V-EBM.**

493

494 **Supplementary Fig. 14. Snippet at 45 Hz of the response of the optimized V-EBM to the**
 495 **frequency sweep test. Top:** Timeseries of elongation and velocity. *Middle:* Timeseries of
 496 contraction and contraction rate. *Bottom:* Power-to-mass timeseries.

497

498 **Supplementary Fig. 15. Cycle average work and average power as functions of applied force**
 499 **at an actuation frequency of 5 Hz. Left:** Three-unit preliminary V-EBM. *Right:* Single-unit
 500 optimized V-EBM.

501

502 **Supplementary Fig. 16. Cyclic average power as function of actuation frequency for the**
 503 **optimized V-EBM subject to a constant force of 1.5 N.**

504

505 **Supplementary Fig. 17. Cycle life test.** The cycle life was characterized at a voltage of 4 kV and
 506 a preload of 1.5 N. The actuator demonstrates at least 500.000 cycles of operation.

507

508 **Supplementary Fig. 18. The intersected stiffness characteristics of the three-unit preliminary**
 509 **V-EBM and of the gripper.** The two characteristics were determined independently: the V-EBM
 510 stress-strain curves were extracted from the envelope of the force ramp tests (6 kV, 5 Hz actuation),
 511 whereas the gripper elastic response was measured in atmosphere with force and displacement

512 sensors. The blue curve describes the elastic deformation of the deactivated actuator during
513 loading; the red curve describes the deformation of the actuator under load when powered; the
514 yellow line shows the loading curve of the gripper elastic deformation (i.e., during gripper closure).
515 The figure is indicative as the real-time states of the combined system may differ due to the elastic
516 hysteresis in its two components. The figure also indicates the working point that quantifies (on
517 the horizontal axis) the gripper and the V-EBM deformation to grasp the rock in Fig. 5 and the
518 required force (vertical axis) to deform the gripper into the grasping configuration.

519 **SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES**

520 **Supplementary Table 1. Dimensions of the components employed in the V-EBMs.** *The
 521 electrodes have small rectangular appendages with a surface of 2 x 5 mm².

Component	Thickness (μm)	Inner diameter (mm)	Outer diameter (mm)
PI dielectric	25	0	45
Electrode*	0.01	16	30
VHB adhesive	500	0	16
Tesa adhesive	100	30	40
Nitto adhesive	5		
FR4 Frame	500		
Pyralux adhesive	25		34
PI frame	500		

522 **Supplementary Table 2. Irradiation parameters and absorbed dose values for the 4**
 523 **irradiated samples of PI.** Values taken from the irradiation report provided by the ENEA facility.

Dose intensity in the beginning (kGy _{water} /h)	Dose intensity in the end (kGy _{water} /h)	Duration (hh:mm:ss)	Absorbed dose (kGy _{water})
2.46	2.46	47:33:26	117.08
	2.45	193:02:30	474.50
	2.44	417:53:42	1025.08
	2.43	602:23:59	1475.41

524 **Supplementary Table 3. Relevant parameters of some voice coil actuators comparable in**
 525 **terms of output stroke and force to the V-EBM.** It is important to note that actuator
 526 manufacturers do not typically provide the temperature increase, because it depends heavily on
 527 application conditions, such as mounting material, contact surface, driving signal, etc.; thermal
 528 behavior often being considered an application-specific parameter. *Values estimated in
 529 supplementary information Section 9.

Actuator	Thorlabs VC063 (21)	H2W Technologies NCC01-12-004-1C (22)	H2W Technologies NCC03-07-001-1V (22)	H2W Technologies NCC03-14-010-1SL (22)	V-EBM unit
Stroke (mm)	6.4	2	6.4	7.1	1
Force 100% duty (N)	0.592 at 0.8 A	2	0.53	4.5	4.2 at 6 kV
Moving mass (g)	7	7.5	7	49	~ 0.2 (top side constrained)

Current 100% duty (A)	0.8 at 1.85 V and 60 °C	2.6	Not specified Est. 0.2	Not specified Est. 1.2	-
Coil resistance at 20 °C (Ω)	1.9	0.9	9.6	5.8	-
Dissip. Power (W)	1.2 (0.8 A at 60 °C)	6	0.4 at 100% duty 3.6 at 10% duty	8 at 100% duty 69 at 10% duty	Est. 10 ⁻⁶ (DC) to 10 ⁻⁴ (100 Hz actuation) *
Temperature increase	Coil temperature increases up to 80 °C, in air, from ambient 22 °C.	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	7.5 °C at 5 kV and 100 Hz in vacuum (no convection).
Vacuum compatibility	Not specified	Not specified	Vacuum compatible	Vacuum compatible	Vacuum compatible
Notes			Manufactured with NASA-selected low-outgassing materials; includes aluminum bobbin for heat dissipation.	Features slotted aluminum bobbin for heat conduction; constructed with low-outgassing materials.	Fabricated using space-compatible materials.

530

531

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